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GENDER INEQUALITY, GOVERNANCE AND SUSTAINABLE HUMAN DEVELOPMENT IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

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Abstract: The role of good governance in reducing the gender inequality and by extension ensuring sustainable human development is gaining much attention in the literature. Thus, this study investigated the combined effect of gender inequality and governance on sustainable human development in Sub-Saharan Africa, using panel data of 44 countries from secondary sources. The study explored the link using quantile regression techniques within a panel setting and found evidence that gender inequality has an adverse effect on sustainable human development in SSA. It also revealed that good governance improves sustainable human development in SSA countries with high human development index, while also empirically revealing that good governance acts as a substitute to gender inequality in improving sustainable human development in SSA. The study therefore recommended that policy makers in Sub-Saharan African countries should promote inclusive and accountable governance structures, strengthen regulatory quality and fight corruption that fast-track the implementation of gender-equitable policies are fully implemented.

Keywords: Gender inequality, Good governance, Human development, Panel quantile regression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, every developed and developing country strives to enshrine an improved human development, accompanied with environmental sustainability and equity in all facets of the society (Etudaiye-Muhtar, Johan, Lawal & Sakariyahu, 2024). Efforts aimed at improving human development and ensures social equity is known as sustainable human development, usually measured using the Human Development Index (HDI) (United Nations, 2023). However, improving human development in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) has been hindered by many factors including gender inequality and weak governance, which eventually affects meeting sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Workneh, Eshete & Figari, 2019).

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The condition of human development in SSA may be attested to by its position when compared to other regions in the world. The United Nations Development Program (2024) reported that the HDI for Sub-Saharan Africa is 0.568, in comparison to the Caribbean 0.783, Arab countries 0.719, while 0.672, 0.739 and 0.916 were reported for South Asia, Small Island developing countries and high-income OECD countries respectively. Similarly, SSA has one of the highest indexes in terms of gender inequality with an index value of 0.558, below 0.539, 0.458 and 0.451 for Arab countries, South Asia and Small Island countries (UNDP, 2023).

Notwithstanding these poor records, SSA has made little progress in increasing female enrollment in primary education and the adoption of gender quotas in countries like Rwanda, which boasts one of the highest proportions of women in parliament globally (UNDP, 2024). However, compounding the little progress made in bridging the gender inequality gap is weak governance structures in SSA. The region is facing the challenges of corruption, government ineffectiveness, and lack of accountability, which worsen the adverse effects of gender inequality (Workneh, *et al*, 2019). Over 60% of SSA countries score below 50 out of 100 in governance indicators as reported by (Ibrahim Index of African Governance, 2024), reflecting weak governance and inefficiencies in policy enforcement. Having weak governance leads to misallocation of resources, undermining initiatives aimed at reducing gender inequality and hindering sustainable development (UNDP, 1997). As a result, the region continues to lag behind global averages in human development rankings, with countries like South Sudan and the Central African Republic among the lowest globally. From the foregoing, the study seeks to examine how gender inequality and governance interact to influence sustainable human development in SSA.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

The term human development is conceptualized to mean all aspects of life relating to health, education, and income, (Uddin, 2023). Thus, sustainable human development is defined as improvement in human wellbeing through enhancement in health, education, and income while maintaining environmental sustainability and social equity for present and future generations (United Nations, 2023). The concept of human development is a multidimensional concept measured using the human development index (HDI), which is a composite measure developed by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to assess and compare the levels of development of countries of the world (UNDP, 2021).

Gender Inequality is seen as the systematic disparities between individuals based on gender, particularly in terms of access to education, healthcare, economic opportunities, and political representation (Klasen & Lamanna, 2009; UNDP, 2023). Indicators used to measure gender inequality. Moreover, the World Bank (1994) defined governance as the structures, processes, and traditions that determine how power is exercised, how decisions are made, and how citizens or other stakeholders have their say.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical foundation for understanding human development in this context is provided by the capability theory, developed by Sen (1980). The capability theory argued that human development is about expanding freedoms (Sen, 1999). As a result, gender inequality restricts women's freedoms, such as access to education or mobility, which limits national capabilities and overall development. However, according to good governance

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theory, good governance enshrines strong institutional and sound economic policies that are pivotal in eliminating restrictions which limits capabilities (World Bank, 1994).

According to the governance theory as introduced by the (World Bank, 1994), good governance is a vital in the formation and shaping of institutional and sound economic policies that are pivotal in creating and sustaining policy environment which fosters strong and sustainable development. The governance theory emphasizes accountability, rule of law and control of corruption as structures of strong governance institutions that drive development (Kaufmann, Kraay & Mastruzzi. 2010). Thus, well-functioning institutions ensure efficient allocation of resources, equitable service delivery, and protection of rights, thereby creating gender equality which is central to expanding capabilities and eventually enhancing sustainable human development.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Yin et al. (2023) investigated the direct and influencing effects of digitalization on gender disparity in labor force participation rates within G20 countries from 2006 to 2021. Based on panel data analysis, the study revealed that higher levels of digitalization tend to diminish the gender gap in employment participation rates to a greater extent in rich countries than in poor countries. However, outcomes diverged notably according to income levels: this interplay was inclined to reduce the gender gap in rich countries with high income but exacerbate it in middle income and lower income countries. Furthermore, the study revealed that digitalization generally increases the female employment rate and decreases female unemployment, while it shows contrasting effects on males. This increase in female employment was particularly prominent within the services sector.

Shah, & Krishnan, (2023) examined the direct and indirect effects of ICT on gender equality and income inequality using data from 86 countries between 2013 and 2016. The study employed the cross-lagged panel analysis of 86 countries and found that ICT can be a useful tool in altering gender inequality, implying that ICT may be used to effect gender equality. The study also showed an inverse linkage between ICT and gender disparity, suggesting that ICT can serve as an instrument supporting women and consequently diminish gender disparities. Also, the study revealed that positive relationship between gender inequality and income inequality in a country.

Moreover, Mahmoodi and Maddah (2023) examined the effect of gender inequality and governance on human development in Economic Cooperation Organization (ECO) comprising of Afghanistan, Iran, Pakistan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan using panel data from 2010-2019. The study applied the panel random effect technique for data analysis and the result showed that gender inequality has an adverse profound effect on human development and index of governance indicators has favourable effect on human development. In the same vein, Altuzarra, Gálvez-Gálvez, and González-Flores, (2021) investigated the effect of various indicators of gender inequality-education, labour market and institutions-on economic growth in SSA from 1990-2017. The study adopted the two-step system GMM and the result of the study revealed that gender equality in education contributes to economic growth in SSA, but found that female - male labour market participation ratio not statistically significant. It also found that a negative relationship between the presence of women in parliaments and growth in SSA.

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$$Q_{hdi}(\tau / x_i) = \beta_{1\tau} GII_{i,t} + \beta_{2\tau} GOV_{i,t} + \beta_{3\tau} GDPGR_{i,t} + \beta_{4\tau} FEM_{i,t} + \beta_{5\tau} (GII * GOV)_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \dots 2$$

Where HDI_{it} represents human development index, GII_{it} represents gender inequality index, FEM_{it} is female employment, and GOV_{it} is government effectiveness. The control variables are GDPGR representing GDP growth rate. The panel quantile equation specified in equation 2 is a quantile regression estimated as pooled OLS estimators. The general process of the quantile equation specified in equation 2 is to use varying values of τ bound between 0 and 1 which yields the regression quantiles for varying distributions of human development index. The study estimation is carried out using the 0.25, 0.50 and 0.75 quantiles, i.e., $\tau = (0.25, 0.5 \text{ and } 0.75)$. These quantiles represent SSA countries with lower level HDI, medium level HDI, as high level HDI.

In analyzing the interaction effect of governance and gender inequality on human development in SSA, it is expected that β_6 (the interaction term) in the model to be significant as it ascertains if governance interacts with gender inequality to make the difference in the level of sustainable human development among the SSA countries. The interaction term could have a significant positive effect, signifying that governance complement gender inequality effect on sustainable human development, while a negative significant signifies that governance acts as a substitute the effect of gender inequality in improving sustainable human development in SSA.

3.2 Technique of Data Analysis

The technique of analysis started with the descriptive statistics and the skewness and kurtosis statistics for the normality tests. The quantile estimation is carried out using three human development index (HDI) levels peculiar to SSA countries, according to the UNDP classifications which are lower HDI, medium HDI, higher HDI. Thereafter, the normality of the series is conducted to check whether the data were suitable for quantile estimation.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the data used in the study, showing the number of observations, mean, maximum and minimum values of the variables.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev	Minimum	Maximum
HDI	623	0.53749	0.10333	0.33	0.817
FEMP	620	305.706	178.213	1	27.302
GOV	630	-0.76138	0.61338	-1.97706	1.15004
GII	535	0.55692	0.07951	0.298	0.72
GDPGR	630	3.66654	4.63199	-36.392	21.45

Source: Authors computation, 2025

The mean value of human development index (HDI) for the period covered in the study is 0.53, implying that on average the HDI level in Sub-Saharan Africa is 0.53 which is a low HDI level, with Mauritius having the highest HDI level of 0.817, while Niger and Chad have the lowest level of 0.3. Also the average gender inequality index in SSA for the study period is 0.55, while governance is -0.76.

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Table 2 presents the correlation matrix of the variables used in the study. The results indicate that the regressors used in this study are not highly correlated as none has a correlation coefficient of 0.8 and above. This implies that there is no incidence of multicollinearity among the independent in the estimated models.

Table 2: The Correlation Matrix

<i>Variables</i>	<i>HDI</i>	<i>FEMP</i>	<i>GOV</i>	<i>GII</i>	<i>GDPPC</i>
<i>HDI</i>	1.0000				
<i>FEMP</i>	-0.2280	1.0000			
<i>GOV</i>	0.4956	-0.2181	1.0000		1.0000
<i>GII</i>	-0.4952	0.3258	-0.6704	1.0000	
<i>GDPGR</i>	-0.0557	0.1992	0.0680	0.0862	

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

4.2 Panel Quantile Regression

The results of the panel quantile regression showing the interaction of gender inequality and governance are presented in Tables 3 and their normality tests shown in Table 4. Since the countries have different HDI levels which are categorized into low HDI, medium HDI and high HDI according the UNDP ranking, the estimated quantile groups are the 25th, 50th, and 75th quantiles. These quantile levels were selected to reflect Sub-Saharan African countries HDI levels with majority of the countries at the lowest HDI level and middle HDI level.

Table 3: The 25th, 50th and 75th Quantile Results

Dependent Variable: HDI

Variable:	25 th quantile			50 th quantile			75 th quantile		
	Coefficie	Std.	Prob.	Coefficie	Std.	Prob.	Coefficie	Std.	Prob.
GII	-0.37907	0.07615	0.000	-0.38021	0.0141	0.000	-0.45079	0.01788	0.000
	0.000014	0.00000	0.040	0.00048	0.00008	0.000	0.00025	0.00003	0.000
FEMP		7							
	-	0.02171	0.264	-0.01774	0.01358	0.192	0.07098	0.00297	0.000
GOV	0.024239								
GDPGR	-0.00133	0.00024	0.000	-0.0005	0.00023	0.031	0.0014	0.00024	0.000
	0.005201	0.01800	0.773	-0.09972	0.00532	0.000	-0.02222	0.00792	0.005
GII*GOV		9							
Mcmc	0.258								
diagnostics	0.289						0.399		

Source: Author's computation, 2025

The results across the 25th, 50th and 70th quantiles in SSA quantiles show that gender inequality has a negative significant effect on sustainable human development in SSA. This means as gender inequality increases in SSA by a unit, sustainable human development decreases by 0.37, 0.38 and 0.45 units respectively across the three quantile groups of human development. This result is expected since low value of gender inequality index

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means low gender inequality whereas; high index value means high gender inequality. The outcome of this result corresponds with the findings of (Altuzarra, et al, 2021) for SSA countries, (Mahmoodi & Maddah, 2023) for countries in the Economic Cooperation Organization, and (Dupe, 2021) for the Nigerian economy. All these studies pointed that gender inequality has an adverse profound effect on human development indicators. Similarly, the outcome tallies with (Shah, & Krishnan, 2023) who found that gender inequality increases income inequality in a country.

Also, the study found that female employment is positive and statistically significant across the three quantile groups used in the study. Although, the effect of female employment is very small, but a unit increase in female employment leads to a small proportional change in sustainable human development across the human development quantile groups in SSA, with the effect higher in the countries at the high HDI level. This is in line with previous findings of (Yin et al., 2023) who found gender gap in employment is reduced in rich countries due to the influence of digitalization.

However, governance has different outcomes across the three quantile groups; it is negative in the 25th and 50th quantile groups and has no significant effect on sustainable human development. In the 75th quantile governance has a significant positive effect on sustainable human development in SSA, a unit increase in governance increases human development by 0.07 units. This result is in tandem with that of (Mahmoodi & Maddah, 2023) who found that governance indicators has favourable effect on human development for countries in the Economic Cooperation Organization. Similarly, the effect of the interaction between gender inequality and governance is negative and significant in the second and third quantile suggesting that good governance serve as a substitute for gender inequality in improving sustainable human development in countries at middle and high HDI levels. The interaction effect is stronger in the high HDI (75th) quantile group than in the 50th quantile level, though no interaction at the lower quantile group. This outcome has been rarely reported in empirical literature.

4.3: The Quantile Regression Normality Tests

Table 4: Shapiro-Wilk, Shapiro-Francia and Skewness Tests

Variables	Shapiro-Wilk test	Skewness/Kurtosis
HDI	7.691 (0.00000)	46.95 (0000)
GII	6.776 (0.00000)	39.88 (0000)
FEMP	7.123 (0.00000)	(0000)
GOV	6.822 (0.00000)	37.45 (0000)
GDPGR	10.092 (0.00000)	7.23 (0000)

Source: Author's computation, 2024

Shapiro wilk test, skewness and kurtosis test. The numbers in brackets are the probability values.

To validate the use of the quantile regression in the study, the Shapiro-Wilk and Skewness/Kurtosis tests are carried out as depicted In Table 4, and the results show that all the variables are statistically significant, which revealed that our variables are not normally distributed supporting the use of panel quantile regression.

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5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the effect of gender inequality and governance on sustainable human development in Sub-Saharan Africa. Using data from secondary sources covering 2010 through 2023 for 44 SSA countries and quantile panel econometric techniques, the study found evidence that gender inequality has an adverse effect on sustainable human development in SSA. It also revealed that good governance improves sustainable human development in SSA countries with high human development index, while also empirically revealing that good governance acts as a substitute to gender inequality in improving sustainable human development in SSA.

Base on the result, it is obvious that the interaction effect of gender inequality and governance has profound implications for sustainable human development in SSA. Thus, there is the need to enshrine quality and effective government, strong regulatory quality and curb corruption, all of which can amplify the impact of gender-equitable policies by ensuring resources reach marginalized groups, while strong and inclusive governance structures that empower women can enhance policy formulation and implementation.

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APPENDIX 1

COUNTRIES USED IN THE STUDY

Angola, Burundi, Benin, Burkina Faso, Botswana, Cape verde, Central African Republic, Cameroon, Chad, Democratic Republic of Congo, Congo Republic, Comoros, Cote d’Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Ghana, The Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Guinea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Mali, Mozambique, Mauritania, Mauritius, Malawi, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome Principe, Seychelles, Sudan, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

APPENDIX 2

Table 2a: Descriptive Statistics, Correlation matrix and Quantile Results

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
hdi	623	.5374976	.1033347	.33	.817
fem	620	305.7065	178.2135	1	613
gov	630	-.7613819	.6133838	-1.977062	1.15004
gii	535	.5569234	.0795065	.298	.72
gdpgr	630	3.666541	4.63199	-36.39198	21.45206

	hdi	fem	ove	gii	gdpgr
hdi	1.0000				
fem	-0.2280	1.0000			
gov	0.4956	-0.2181	1.0000		
gii	-0.4952	0.3258	-0.6704	1.0000	
gdpgr	-0.0557	0.1992	0.0680	0.0862	1.0000

25th Quantile (0.25)

Quantile Regression for Panel Data (QRPD)

Number of obs: 531
 Number of groups: 41
 Min obs per group: 5
 Max obs per group: 14

hdi	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]
gii	-.3790797	.0761595	-4.98	0.000	-.5283495 -.2298099
fem	.0000147	7.14e-06	2.05	0.040	6.65e-07 .0000286
geff	-.0242393	.0217099	-1.12	0.264	-.0183113 .0667898
gdpgr	-.0013362	.0002381	-5.61	0.000	-.0018028 -.0008695

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interaction1 | .0052008 .0180091 0.29 0.773 -.0300963 .0404979

 No excluded instruments - standard QRPD estimation.

MCMC diagnostics:

Mean acceptance rate: 0.258
 Total draws: 1000
 Burn-in draws: 100
 Draws retained: 900
 Value of objective function:
 Mean: -11.5420
 Min: -20.6272
 Max: -6.0159

MCMC notes:

- *Point estimates correspond to mean of draws.
- *Standard errors are derived from variance of draws.

50th Quantile (0.5)

Quantile Regression for Panel Data (QRPD)

Number of obs: 531
 Number of groups: 41
 Min obs per group: 5
 Max obs per group: 14

hdi	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
gii	-.380209	.0140999	-26.97	0.000	-.4078443	-.3525736
fem	.000485	8.58e-05	5.65	0.000	-.0000653	-.0000317
geff	-.0177356	.0135878	-1.31	0.192	-.0443672	.008896
gdpr	-.0005018	.0002333	-2.15	0.031	-.000959	-.0000446
interaction1	-.0997262	.0053237	-18.73	0.000	-.1101604	-.089292

No excluded instruments - standard QRPD estimation.

MCMC diagnostics:

Mean acceptance rate: 0.289
 Total draws: 1000
 Burn-in draws: 100
 Draws retained: 900
 Value of objective function:

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Mean: -43.3760
Min: -53.2634
Max: -38.7845

MCMC notes:

*Point estimates correspond to mean of draws.

*Standard errors are derived from variance of draws.

75th quantile (0.75)

Quantile Regression for Panel Data (QRPD)

Number of obs: 531
Number of groups: 41
Min obs per group: 5
Max obs per group: 14

hdi	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
gii	-.4507933	.0178835	-25.21	0.000	-.4858443	-.4157422
fem	.000246	3.01e-05	8.19	0.000	-.0000305	-.0000187
geff	.0709825	.0029744	23.86	0.000	.0651529	.0768121
gdpgr	.0014031	.0002419	5.80	0.000	-.0018772	-.0009291
interaction1	-.0222253	.0079203	-2.81	0.005	-.0377488	-.0067017

No excluded instruments - standard QRPD estimation.

MCMC diagnostics:

Mean acceptance rate: 0.399
Total draws: 1000
Burn-in draws: 100
Draws retained: 900
Value of objective function:
Mean: -28.3921
Min: -37.6462
Max: -20.2269